

ISic0638

I.Sicily inscription 0638

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Ipogeo Arancio

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Villa Landolina?

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Μ(ἄρκος) Κοκκήϊς
2. Νεικηφόρος
3. χρηστὲ · καὶ · ἄμεμ
4. πτε · χαῖρε ·
5. ἔζησε · ἔτη · γ

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro 1994

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644880

PHI 332969

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0761

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0792

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 84 no.2 fig.4

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